

Description of elastic and plastic properties of microstructures on high-performance surfaces of transmission parts by means of angle-resolved scattered light method

Presenter:

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Abstract

Function-oriented parameters of the contact mechanics of rough surfaces are derived and related to classical parameters from technical standards. A new optical method that is highly related to these functional parameters is presented and measurements on gear surfaces of FZG test specimens of initial and wear surfaces are shown.

Keywords: Mixed friction, surface roughness, scattered light method.

1. Introduction

A function-oriented tolerancing of technical surfaces in tribological systems is one of the central elements of efficient industrial production. Without knowing the relevant criteria, it is difficult for the development department, quality assurance and production to identify the right processing and measuring methods, which are necessary for high product quality and high cost-effectiveness at the same time. In recent years, new manufacturing processes such as polish grinding have been established in the processing of the gear geometry, but practical quality assurance of the necessary surface structures still represents a major challenge. On the one hand, finer microstructures push the existing measuring technologies to the limits of measuring equipment capability and, at the same time, the usual parameters of the standard are no longer sufficient to adequately describe the functional behavior of fine machined parts. In the following, meaningful parameters are to be derived from the requirements of contact mechanics on surfaces and a measurement method is to be presented that fulfills both, the functional relationship and the necessary quality assurance criteria with regard to calibration and traceability [1]. The scattered light method described below is already used in the assessment of tooth flanks in worm gears in steering systems with high efficiency requirements [2] and is described by the VDA as a method for assessing tribologically demanding surfaces in a separate VDA recommendation [3].

2. Loaded surfaces in tribological systems.

Two workpiece surfaces that interact with each other experience a force that opposes their relative motion to each other, the frictional force [4]. Although the underlying phenomenological equation of Coulomb's law of friction is simple in structure,

$$F_f = f \cdot F_N \quad (1)$$

friction coefficient f itself is a complex interaction of all the components involved in the tribological system. Figure 1 schematically shows the change in the coefficient of friction as a function of the relative movement of the friction partners in a lubricated sliding contact [4]. Depending on the speed v , there are different friction conditions. Above the critical speed v_{cr} , the two friction partners are completely separated by the lubricating gap height h and the load F_n is only absorbed by the hydrodynamic load capacity of the lubricant. If the lubricating gap falls below the critical gap height h_{cr} , the friction state changes from pure liquid friction F_{fh} to

Figure 1) schematic Stribeck curve for lubricated tribological systems according to Bartel [4]

the state of mixed friction, which is increasingly dominated by dry friction F_{fs} and thus by the contacts of the surface asperities as the lubricating gap height decreases. Ideally, these asperities should therefore be as low as possible in order to enable separation even at low speeds. In practice, however, tribological systems are mainly operated in the mixed friction range, so that the properties of the asperities should not be neglected when designing the system. It should also be considered here that, taking into account the elastic and plastic properties of the solid bodies involved, every fully lubricated EHD contact is already part of the mixed friction and this can therefore also occur without direct contact of the asperities [4]. The behavior of micro-contacts between solids is described to a good approximation by the plasticity index ψ of the Greenwood-Williamson model [5]. This considers the statistical character of rough surfaces, taking into account the local properties of the individual contact. Whether a microcontact behaves plastically or elastically depends mainly on the material properties, Young's modulus E^* and hardness σ_0 , the mean square height deviation of the roughness asperities R_q and their mean radii of curvature R . The plasticity index ψ is defined as

$$\psi \approx \frac{4}{3\pi} \cdot \frac{E^*}{\sigma_0} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{R_q}{R}} \quad (2)$$

It gives a good indication of how the contacts of the microstructures behave and how large the real contact area becomes under load. If $\psi > 1$, the micro-contacts are completely plastically deformed, in an interval of $1/2 < \psi < 1$ a mixture of plastic and elastic deformations can be expected, while with $\psi < 1/2$ the purely elastic state occurs [6]. The real contact area, which is

of fundamental importance for dry friction, increases with the plastic deformation of the roughness asperities [4]. Since the functional behavior of the tribological system in the mixed friction area depends not only on the material properties of the friction partners, but also on the contact geometry, this is of crucial importance for the selection of the surface finish and also for the selection of the surface parameters.

3. Characterization of surfaces with a tribological function

The tolerance of technical surfaces of transmission components is based on the specifications of DIN3990 [7]. Here, the height parameter Rz is recommended as a scalar quantity in the formula for calculating the flank load-bearing capacity. As a result, this parameter becomes a central element of the product specification and thus of quality assurance. It is defined according to ISO4287 [8] as the mean value of the largest height differences that occur in 5 sections of the same length of the profile.

$$Rz = \frac{1}{5} \sum_{i=1}^5 Z_i \quad (3)$$

So only the 10 local extreme values of the signal are evaluated and all other recorded height values have no influence on the result. As a result, a lot of profile information is lost and the statistical character of the surface roughness is extremely reduced. Although the Rz value gives a better idea of the maximum expansion of a workpiece than the simple and frequently used parameter of the mean roughness value Ra , it does not contain any information about the actual height distribution. At the same time, the small number of height values used for the calculation means that the measured Rz value depends heavily on the environmental conditions. The finer the tolerance, the greater the environmental impact. In (2) the standard deviation of the asperity heights Rq is used as a parameter to determine the height part of the

Figure 2) Surface profiles with identical Rz values and different amplitude density distributions

plasticity index ψ and the critical lubrication gap height h_{cr} can be derived from this statistical analysis for normally distributed surfaces. It can be assumed that the majority of the heights are in a range of 3 standard deviations around the zero line and this range offers a good indication of the critical height h_{cr} [4]. However, most technical surfaces are not normally

distributed in character and more information about asperities is needed. Further parameters of the amplitude density distribution are suitable here. The well-known R_a value is found as the 1st moment, the R_q as the 2nd moment and the profile skewness R_{sk} as the 3rd moment of the amplitude distribution [9]. For clarification, Figure 2 shows profiles with identical height values R_a and R_z and correspondingly a different height distribution. In the case of the tribologically more favorable profile b, the extreme values of the profile that forms the R_z are obviously more pronounced in the negative range, while the gaussian distributed profile a has extreme values in both directions of the zero-profile line and therefore requires a higher critical lubricating film height h_{cr} . From theoretical considerations, the profile skewness R_{sk} seems to be suitable for characterizing the surface, but it is very susceptible to outliers due to the strong weighting of the extreme values in the third power. For a practicable characterization of the surface in terms of quality assurance, however, measurement variables are necessary which on the one hand address the statistical character of the surface and at the same time are robust to extreme value outliers. On the one hand, this requires that enough individual values from a measurement are taken into account to form the characteristic value and that the evaluation method is suitable for mapping the profile properties with sufficient accuracy. R_a and R_q are very robust compared to R_z , but they also do not contain any information about the type of height distribution. The integrated amplitude density, which is known in tribology as the Abbott/Firestone or bearing area curve (BAC), is particularly suitable [10]. To put it simply, the individual height values are sorted in descending magnitude and plotted over the measurement length. It indicates the proportion of material in a defined cutting depth. Starting at 0%, the height of the first profile contact and ending with the smallest value, as the limit to

figure 3) Profiles with identical BACs

the material undisturbed by roughness. Research by Bodschwinn et al were able to show in the 1980s on the basis of cylinder liner surfaces that the three-line model of ISO13656 is suitable as a very good approximation of the bearing area curve and that the parameters derived from it, R_{pk} as reduced peak height, R_k as core roughness depth and R_{vk} as reduced groove depth, deliver robust parameters, which are able to enable practical tolerances of the height properties of a topography [11]. However, Figure 3 clearly shows that the surface

characterization based solely on height information is incomplete. Both profiles shown have an identical distribution of the heights and thus the BAC. The decisive difference can be found in the form of the asperities and their radii of curvature. This means that the possible real contact areas of these two surfaces are fundamentally different despite identical BAC. This is a surface property that is particularly important when the friction partners involved in the tribological system are not completely separated by a lubricating film or have fully lubricated EHD contact [4].

The quotient $\sqrt{Rq/R}$ used in (2) is directly related to the profile slopes of the surface and can be found as

$$\Delta q = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\theta_i - \bar{\theta})^2} \quad (4)$$

in the literature. In ISO4287 it is described as Rdq for the analog case and $R\Delta q$ for the digital case [8] as the root mean square gradient. Similar to the mean square profile height Rq , it can also be interpreted as the standard deviation of a density distribution. This makes it clear that characterizing surfaces is a multivariate problem and several independent variables must be

figure 4) Angle (gradient)- and amplitude distribution of profile d and c of figure 5

considered. Figure 4 shows the gradient- and height- distributions of profiles c and d from Figure 3, as well as the parameters derived from them. Here it is noticeable that the majority of standardized roughness parameters can be found in the area of height properties, but these are completely unsuitable for the geometric component required in (2). This is due to the fact that the usual measuring devices have an excellent transmission behavior for height information, but the slope information is obtained from the first numerical derivative. This makes them significantly dependent on sample density and any noise superimposed on the roughness signal [12]. Despite their theoretical importance, they cannot provide reliable surface information and are understandably ignored by the industry as a quality feature.

4. Characterization of surfaces using the scattered light method according to VDA2009.

In contrast to the measuring methods for the direct measurement of surface profiles and

Figure 5) Measuring principle

surface topographies, the scattered light method according to VDA2009 is one of the surface-integrating methods. An exact system-theoretical description can be found in [13]. The method combines a scatterometer with a deflectometer and offers the possibility to measure roughness and shape at the same time. Figure 5 shows the measuring principle in a rough sketch. A light source (not in the sketch) illuminates a rough surface perpendicularly with red LED light. According to the model of the mirror facets, the impinging rays of light are now reflected by the slope of the roughness. Because of the law of reflection, their reflection angle φ_i corresponds to twice the angle of the surface flank angle θ_i . A scattered light optic collects the light and transmits it to a point in the focal plane that is associated with this angle. Each ray of light reflected at the same angle φ_i thus reaches the same point. The ratio of the light intensity $I(\varphi_i)$ to the total amount of light $\sum I(\varphi_i)$ corresponds to the relative frequency $p(\varphi_i)$ of the scattering angle φ_i on the surface. Using the relationship

$$\varphi_i = 2 \cdot \theta_i \quad (5)$$

the frequency distribution of the surface profile angles is measured, which is identical to the gradient distribution shown in Figure 6 because of the small-angle approximation. The variance of the scattering angle distribution is denoted by Aq in the VDA2009 (A for Angle) and is identical to Δq^2 from (4) except for a constant factor.

$$Aq = k \cdot \sum_{i=1}^N (\varphi_i - \bar{\varphi})^2 \cdot p(\varphi_i) \approx \Delta q^2 \quad (6)$$

The parameter Aq is therefore a measure of the gradient distribution within the illuminated area. Analogously to the parameters of the amplitude density distribution, the higher moments m_3 and m_4 are also defined as parameters. Ask stands for profile angle skewness and Aku for kurtosis. In the literature, m_4 can also be interpreted as the variance of the radii of curvature [14]. Applications for skewness can be found in [15]. By evaluating the center of gravity $\bar{\varphi}$, the longwave form deviation can be calculated by integration and displayed as a topography if the distance between the measuring points is known.

5. Measurement of gear flanks according to VDA2009.

Figure 6 shows a laboratory setup for measuring scattered light on straight tooth flanks. The measurement spot *b* is projected onto the surface of the test object *c* using a deflection prism *a*. The component is moved linearly in the *x* direction (red arrow in the picture) using an *x/y* scanning table (not shown in the picture). By changing the position by *dy* after each scan, the tooth flank surface is completely scanned from tip to root circle. A total of 123,750 individual *Aq* values were recorded on an area of 11.0 x 4.5mm and plotted on their *x/y* coordinates and

figure 6) Measurement setup (left) and area measurement (right), before the test (above) and after the test run (below)

their scalar value color-coded so that their distribution over the tooth flank can be seen.

It is to be expected that the asperities will change during the run-in and operation of the test specimen. A fully lubricated EHD contact should create a more favorable operating surface during run-in by flattening the contact points. As shown in Figure 6, larger radii of curvature should result in flatter slopes and smaller variance *Aq*. The result of the test shows the following changes:

The initial surface starts at an average level of the *Aq* of 56. After the stress test on the FZG test bench, severe wear marks (scuffing) were found in the tip area. This can be seen clearly from the strong decrease in the variance *Aq* in the direction of loading. The original asperities of the grinding marks have been completely replaced by those of the scuffing marks, while the rest of the surface has undergone a more moderate change suggesting flattening of the asperities. The tooth flank that has been used has an average *Aq* of 30, which is made up of the worn area with *Aq*15 and a plasticized area with *Aq* 36. It is therefore possible, by using the scattered light method according to VDA2009, to describe the changes in the surface during operation of gears and, in conjunction with the already known quantities of gear measurement, to enable the surface required for optimal operation to be optimized.

6. Conclusion

If tribological systems are operated in the mixed-friction area, their description using only altitude parameters is insufficient. Contact mechanics also requires a characterization of surface slopes and curvatures, which, however, is not sufficiently accurate with topographical

measuring systems. The scattered light method according to VDA2009 is suitable for this, as it can record the necessary parameters directly from the reflection properties of the surface.

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